

Metal-Ligand Stability Constants of Complexes of Substituted Ortho-Hydroxyacetophenones with Bivalent Metal Ions

P. V. KAMAT* & M. G. DATAR

Institute of Science, Bombay 32.

Received 3, October 1969

Metal-ligand stability constants of copper, zinc and cadmium with substituted ortho-hydroxyacetophenones were determined in 75% dioxane—25% water at 30°, potentiometrically. An attempt has been made to correlate properties of metal ions and the substitution in reagents with that of the metal-ligand stability constants.

It is well known that the metal-ligand stability constants are dependent on the properties of metals as well as the ligands taking part in the complex formation. In the case of series of structurally similar compounds the binding forces acting in the complexes should be of the same nature and should be responsible to affect the stability of the complexes thus formed. In such cases the correlation may be obtained between the metals and the structural relationship of the ligands. Compilation of data on the stability constants by Bjerrum and others¹ indicate that the metal complexes of substituted orthohydroxyacetophenones have not been studied systematically from this view point. We, therefore, report such a study.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. *Chemicals* : Copper oxide, zinc oxide and cadmium carbonate of B.D.H. A.R. quality have been used.

B. *Metal salt solutions* : Solutions of metal perchlorate were used to avoid complexing of the metal ions by anions. They were prepared by treating solution of perchloric acid of requisite strength with excess of oxide or carbonate and suitably diluting the resulting neutral solutions. A slightly different method had to be followed for copper perchlorate, since cupric salts hydrolyse at $pH < 6$. An amount of copper oxide exactly equivalent to 10 ml. of approximately equal to 1.6 *M* perchloric acid was dissolved in 20 ml. and was diluted to 100 ml.

C. *Estimation of metal ions* : All metals were estimated by EDTA method².

D. *Bjerrum-Calvin titration* : The method adopted by Irving and Rossotti³ has been used for determination of the proton-ligand stability constants. For the metal-ligand stability constants in addition to acid and reagent titrations, metal titrations were also performed as follows. 5 ml. of $\sim 0.008M$ metal salts in 0.16*M* perchloric acid was taken in a reaction cell, thermostated at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and to this was added 5 ml. of 0.8 *M* sodium perchlorate solution and 5 ml. of the reagent solution along with 25 ml. of dioxane (Dioxane-water ratio 75%–25% v/v). The *pH* measurements were then accomplished in an atmosphere of oxygen-free nitrogen adding approximately 1 *M* alkali till the maximum value of

about pH 12 was reached on an 'Elico- pH meter' model LI-10 (accuracy ± 0.05 pH units) with Beckmann-Glass-saturated calomel electrode assembly to read pH 0-14. The ratio of metal salt to reagent was maintained at very nearly 1 : 4 in all the titrations in order to satisfy the highest possible co-ordination number (viz. 6) of the metal ions under investigation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The plot of V (volume of alkali added) against B (pH meter reading in mixed solvent media) for the systems studied show a considerable displacement along the volume axis of their metal titration curves with respect to the reagent curves. This is due to the liberation of protons from the phenolic $-OH$ groups due to complexation. It is supported by the appearance of the colours distinctly different from those characteristic of the metal ions, non-appearance of any precipitate in the neutral or slightly alkaline solutions and the established chelating tendency of the reagents⁴. In the case of zinc and cadmium the observed displacement of the metal curve would be an evidence since the pair of groups O^- and $C=O$ are known to form chelates^{5,6} with them provided it is not due to metal ion hydrolysis. The polynuclear, hydrogen and hydroxyl bearing and anion complexing may be ignored under the experimental conditions employed here.

Copper system : The plot of \bar{n} against pL for these complexes indicate that in almost all complexes the values of \bar{n} obtained are of the order of 2. In case of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone the observed \bar{n} value is of order of one. This suggests that this, in general, forms two types of complexes in the proportion of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 with the ligands under investigation. In the case of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone only 1 : 1 complex species could be detected. It is also observed that with the compounds 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy acetophenone and 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone \bar{n} values of the order of 2 are reached before the B value of hydrolysis of copper. This suggests that the complex formation occurs in the acid region and, therefore, these complexes should be strong.

Zinc and cadmium systems : The \bar{n} values for the complexes of zinc show that with the exception of 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone and 2-hydroxy-4-methylpropio-phenone, they are greater than 1 but less than 2, indicating the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. However, in the two compounds mentioned above it was observed that there was an abrupt rise in \bar{n} near the B of hydrolysis of zinc ion. This was subsequently followed by the appearance of precipitate at 10.5. It may, therefore, be inferred that in these two cases this metal forms only 1 : 1 stable complex and that the higher complex is either unstable or the mode leading to its formation does not appear to be stepwise. Cadmium on the other hand shows the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with all the ligands without any exception. Further, it is also noticed that in the of hydrolysis of latter case the values of \bar{n} of the order of two are reached in a number of cases before the B cadmium, The relation between B value of hydrolysis of metal ions, colour of solution, precipitation etc. are given in Table I.

Calculation of the formation constants : This is accomplished in two steps : (1) The formation curves are first obtained, (2) these are analysed to arrive at the formation constants. The details of the calculations were similar to that of Jabalpurwala and others⁷. (Usual standard abbreviations are used hereafter).

TABLE I

Relation between B of hydrolysis of the metal ion, colour of solution, precipitation, etc.

Copper System

Comp. No.	Values of Dept. of metal from reagent Curve B	B values at first appearance of colour B	Values at B of metal ion hydrolysis \bar{n}	Values at B of precipitation B
1	~2.10	~3.52	~1.00	9.20
2	~2.40	~3.46	~1.66	8.37
3	~2.65	~3.98	~2.00	7.15
4	~3.20	~2.82	~1.00	10.49
5	~3.00	~4.09	~1.25	6.78
6	~2.80	~2.63	~1.80	7.81
7	~2.10	~4.34	~2.00	—
8	~2.45	~2.77	~1.00	6.75
9	~2.50	~3.28	~1.00	8.32

B of hydrolysis of Copper = 4.9

Zinc System

1	~2.00	~2.12	1.80	—
2	~2.80	~3.42	1.00	10.00
3	~4.90	~3.61	1.00	10.48
4	~4.90	~4.92	1.00	10.04
5	~5.40	~2.85	0.90	8.15
6	~4.75	~9.75	1.80	—
7	~2.70	~3.58	1.80	11.02
8	~5.40	~3.05	0.50	9.93
9	~5.40	~3.98	0.55	9.87

B of hydrolysis of Zinc = 6.1

Cadmium System

1	2.50	1.95	2.00	—
2	2.40	7.70	2.00	11.10
3	5.00	5.35	2.00	11.05
4	4.00	2.53	2.00	8.00
5	3.20	3.16	2.00	7.92
6	5.00	11.27	1.50	—
7	2.40	7.12	2.00	11.45
8	5.20	3.05	1.50	10.95
9	5.20	5.08	1.50	10.83

B of hydrolysis of Cadmium = 7.7.

The metal-ligand stability constants are obtained from \bar{n} , pL data. The values of pL at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 correspond to the log values of first and second stability constants, respectively. In the case of 1 : 1 complexes the formation function is given by

$$\log \frac{1-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}} = pL - \log K_1$$

on rearranging, we get

$$\log K_1 = pL + \log(\bar{n}/1-\bar{n})$$

indicating that the values of $\log(\bar{n}/1-\bar{n})$ are a linear function of pL . For $\log K_2$ the following equation was used

$$\log K_2 = pL + \log(2-\bar{n}/\bar{n}-1)$$

In cases where $\log K_2$ could not be read by either of the methods were calculated by

$$2 \log K_1 K_2 = \log K_1 + \log K_2$$

The values of $\log K_1 K_2$ are obtained by reading them at $\bar{n} = 1.0$ from the \bar{n}/pL graphs. The calculated value of B , \bar{n} and pL are depicted in figs. 1, 2, and 3 and $\log K$ in Table III.

Discussion of log K values : An attempt has been made to compare the observed values of the complexes of the related ligands. Salicylaldehyde, ortho-hydroxypropionophenone and catechol are structurally similar to ortho-hydroxyacetophenones. The data on the complexes of the first transition series metals with these reagents is available in the literature. As far as possible the comparison is restricted to the identical experimental conditions and by the same author, to minimise the errors otherwise involved. The data collected is given in Table II.

TABLE II
Log K₁ and log K₂ values of structurally similar compounds

Ligand		Metals		
		Cu	Zn	Cd
Salicylaldehyde	log K ₁	5.777	6.26	4.62
	log K ₂	2.01	—	(3.14)
2-hydroxyacetophenone	log K ₁	12.06	11.62	11.45
	log K ₂	10.60	8.65	8.67
Catechol	log K ₁	12.92 ^a	8.54	—
	log K ₂	9.93	6.46	—
2-hydroxy propionophenone	log K ₁	10.75	7.52	7.82
	log K ₂	7.45	5.37	5.98

(Values in brackets are investigated under different experimental conditions).

Fig. 1. Copper Complex

Fig. 2. Zinc Complexes

Fig. 3. Cadmium Complexes

No.	Ligand	Symbol
1	2-Hydroxy acetophenone	—————
2	2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-acetophenone	- - - - -
3	2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone	-x-x-x-
4	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone	-▼-▼-▼-
5	2,6-Dihydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone	-○-○-○-
6	2-Hydroxy-4-benzyloxy-acetophenone	-●-●-●-
7	2-Hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy-acetophenone	-◐-◐-◐-
8	2-Hydroxy propiophenone	-■-■-■-
9	2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-propiophenone	-◁-▷-▷-

TABLE III
Metal-ligand stability constants log K₁

Metal	Ligands								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Cu	12.21	10.78	11.12	9.11	8.03	9.59	11.72	10.70	10.40
Zn	11.60	10.06	7.52	8.26	5.62	7.39	10.56	7.51	7.66
Cd	11.46	10.85	7.22	8.09	7.55	6.97	10.93	7.82	7.94
Cu	12.06	10.69	11.20	9.06	7.98	9.60	11.18	10.75	10.47
Zn	11.62	10.08	7.30	8.30	5.52	7.50	10.47	7.52	7.67
Cd	11.45	10.84	7.10	8.04	7.55	7.00	10.93	7.82	7.96

Metal-ligand stability constants log K₂

Metal	Ligands								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Cu	10.64	8.80	10.60	—	5.93	8.24	10.77	7.47	7.38
Zn	8.65	6.42	—	5.70	4.69	5.64	7.56	5.40	—
Cd	8.69	8.28	6.25	6.56	4.37	4.92	6.98	6.06	5.85
Cu	10.60	8.80	10.53	—	5.93	8.28	10.77	7.45	7.38
Zn	8.65	6.40	—	5.74	4.81	5.75	7.57	5.37	(4.37)
Cd	8.67	8.29	6.14	6.61	4.46	4.95	6.97	5.98	5.79

It is quite evident from this data that the log K values for all the complexes of ortho-hydroxyacetophenones are higher than those for the complexes of either salicylaldehyde, ortho-hydroxypropiophenone or catechol. The only exception being that of the copper-catechol complex in which case the log K₁ for the latter is higher. The observed difference between salicylaldehyde and ortho-hydroxyacetophenone may be attributed to the difference in the electronegativity of the two end substituents in the side chain of these two compounds. The presence of a methyl group in ortho-hydroxyacetophenone probably stabilises this compound by increasing the strength of the bond between the metal and the reagent due to the higher inductive effect of this substituent. This reasoning appears to be supported by the observed log K values for the complexes of ortho-hydroxypropiophenone which are intermediate between salicylaldehyde and ortho-hydroxyacetophenone and in which the inductive effect of the ethyl group is less pronounced as compared to that of a methyl group.

The plausible explanation for the slightly higher log K values of ortho-hydroxyacetophenone may be deduced from the following consideration.

The complexation of the metal catechol chelate involves the formation of a five membered ring with only one double bond while those of acetophenone forms a six membered ring with two double bonds.

Further the 1 : 1 catechol chelate with bivalent metal is probably a neutral complex due to the ionisation of both the hydroxyl groups in the reagent. This is not so in the case of ortho-hydroxyacetophenone complexes. If this presumption is accepted then the existence of two canonical forms of a metal complex with the latter reagent is envisaged :

The acetophenone complexes thus attain stability by means of resonance in the chelate ring. In the case of catechol complexes this kind of possibility appears to be non-existent which results in the lower $\log K$ values for these complexes.

A careful study shows that $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values for all the complexes of metals with 2,6-dihydroxy-4-methylacetophenone are the lowest. The authors feel that in this case the complexation takes place preferentially with the second hydroxyl groups which is not involved in the formation of a hydrogen bond with the ketonic oxygen. In these complexes it is felt that the stability is affected by steric factors and the lack of resonance due to the absence of the following structures :

Although the $\log K_1$ values for the metal ions zinc and cadmium are almost same for various ligands it is generally observed that in some cases $\log K_2$ values for cadmium are somewhat higher than those of zinc. The $\log K$ values observed for the metal complexes with 2-hydroxyacetophenone are generally the lowest of all methyl-substituted chelating agents. From the data collected one fails to understand why 2-hydroxy-5-methyl, and 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenones do not form 1 : 2 complexes with copper and zinc, respectively, although the corresponding complexes are formed with the cadmium ions.

The order of $\log K$ values observed in the present study is in partial agreement with the one reported by Irving and Williams⁹ which is accepted as a natural order valid for a given series of metal ions, irrespective of nature of ligands. Zinc and cadmium complexes show $\log K$ values of almost the same order. The only exception being that of complexes with 2,6-dihydroxy-4-methylacetophenone in which the $\log K$ values for the complexes of cadmium is higher than that of zinc by about 2 log units.

The higher values of copper complexes may be explained as follows. The complexes of copper are generally square planer. The O-M-O bond in such structures makes an angle of 90° , whereas the C-O-M bond angle would be 105° . The latter shows little difference from the normal H-O-H bond angle¹⁰. This observation leads to the conclusion that least strain is involved in a square planer structure. This argument also receives support from the observed $\log K$ values for the complexes of nickel which is also known to possess square

planer structure. Further proof in support of the above argument may be obtained from the results of Charles and Feiser¹¹ who found that the log K values for the complexes of copper and nickel with dimethyl glyoxime differ by less than one unit.

REFERENCES

* CIBA Research Centre, Bombay-63, India.

1. J. Bjerrum, G. Schwarzenbach and L. G. Sillen. Stability constants, Part I, 2nd Edition, Chemical Society, London, 1967.
2. G. Schwarzenbach and W. Biedermann, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1948, **31**, 459.
3. H. M. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
4. A. Agren, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 39.
5. Z. L. Earnst and F. G. Herring, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **60**, 498.
6. D. T. Y. Chen and K. J. Laidler, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, **58**, 471.
7. K. E. Jabalpurwala, K. A. Venkatachalam and M. B. Kabadi, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1027.
8. K. S. Math. Proc. Symp. Chem. Co-ordination Compds, Agra, 1959, Part III, p. 65.
9. H. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
10. L. Pauling. The Nature of Chemical Bond, Ithaca, New York, Cornell Univ. Press, 2nd Edition, 1945, p. 79.
11. R. G. Charles and H. Feiser, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1954, **11**, 101.